

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

“SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY OF IVERMECTIN ANALOGUES OF POTENT NSAIDS”

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 17/07/2021

Available online
31/08/2021

Keywords

Ivermectin,
DCC,
DMAP,
Nsaids,
Esterification.

ABSTRACT

A series of novel Ivermectin derivatives are synthesized at position 4''-hydroxyl group of oleandrosyl moiety using Dicyclohexyl cabodiimide (DCC) and Dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP). Derivatives synthesized by Steglich Esterification reaction between variety of carboxyl containing potent NSAIDs and 4''- hydroxyl of Ivermectin. Their chemical structures were characterized by means of IR, 1H NMR. These newly synthesized derivatives tested for in vitro anthelmintic activity against earthworms of species *Pheretima posthuma*. In present work, our aim to synthesize 4''-ester derivatives of Ivermectin with carboxyl containing potent NSAIDs to improve the potency of anthelmintic activity. To develop avermectins modified at the 4''-position, we attempted Steglich Esterification reaction of the 4''-hydroxy derivatives to introduce ester groups in presence of DMAP and DCC. The Steglich Esterification reaction would be useful for esterification between carboxyl and hydroxyl group using dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) as coupling agent and Dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) as catalyst. In this letter, we report the synthesis of new 4''-ester derivatives with potent NSAIDs and their biological activities.

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Please cite this article in press as **Pranita Bapusaheb Chougule et al.** “Synthesis, Characterization and Anthelmintic Activity of Ivermectin Analogues of Potent Nsaids”. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2021:11(08).

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INTRODUCTION

Avermectins, isolated originally from the culture broth of *Streptomyces avermitilis*, are a series of unique 16-membered ring macrolides and have been known to exhibit exceptionally potent anthelmintic, acaricidal, and insecticidal activities.^[1] Ivermectin B1 is the most effective avermectin for insects and mites, and has been commercialized for agricultural use.^[2] Ivermectin, 22,23-dihydroavermectin B1 prepared by regioselective hydrogenation using Wilkinson's catalyst,^[3] has been widely used as an anthelmintic drug in animals, while ivermectin is also used in human for onchocerciasis,^[4] Strongyloidiasis^[5] and lymphatic filariasis.^[6] Since the discovery of ivermectin, various derivatives have been synthesized so far to provide avermectin derivatives having higher and broader spectrum of activity.^[7] In our search for new synthetic avermectins, we focused on chemical modification of the 4''-position on I-oleandrose to improve the activities, because introduction of acyloxy, amino and thio groups at this moiety was found to be effective in terms of solubility, distribution, stability, and diversity of spectrum with potent activity.^[8] Among them, emamectin having an epi methylamino group at the 4''-position was developed as an agricultural insecticide.^[9] Eprinomectin in which the 4''-hydroxyl group is replaced by an epi acetylamino group exhibits potent endectocidal activity with minimal residues in milk, and is used for treatment of lactating dairy cattle parasites.^[10] (Figure no.1)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Worm collection and authentication

Healthy adult Indian earthworms *Pheritima posthuma* due to its anatomical and physiological resemblance with the intestinal roundworm parasites of human beings were used in the present study. The earthworms of 5-7 cm in length and 0.1- 0.2 cm in width were used for all experimental protocol. They were collected from local moist place, washed and kept in water and authenticated.

Melting points were determined by open capillary method using "VMP-I" melting point apparatus and were uncorrected. FTIR spectra were taken on "Jasco FT/IR-410", using KBr pressed pellet technique. The ¹H-NMR spectra were run on a Bruker spectrometer in CDCl₃ (300 MHz) using tetramethylsilane as internal standard. Chemicals were purchased from Aldrich, Himedia and Molychem. All the reactants were identified by comparison of melting points with those reported in the literature.

GENERAL PROCEDURE FOR SYNTHESIS OF 4''- ESTER DERIVATIVE OF IVERMECTIN OF POTENT NSAIDS: ¹¹⁻¹³

3 gm of 22, 23-dihydro avermectin B1a/B1b in 30 ml of dry dimethyl formamide was combined with 1.4gm of Imidazole and stirred at room temperature until all the materials had dissolved. Then 1.56 gm of t-butyl-dimethyl silyl chloride was added and the reaction mixture stirred at room temperature for 70 minutes. The reaction mixture was diluted with 150 ml of ether, water was added and the layers were separated. The aqueous layer was extracted twice more with ether and the combined ether layers washed four times with water and once with saturated sodium chloride solution. The ether layer was dried over magnesium sulphate and concentrated to dryness in vacuo affording 4.2 gm of white foam. Foam is chromatographed to purify the product (**I**).

To 10-25 ml of Methylene chloride added 1.1 mmol of Dicyclohexyl cabodiimide (DCC) and compound (**I**) (1.0 mmol), dissolved it in CH₂Cl₂. Then added 1.0 mmol of carboxylic acid containing NSAIDS and 1.1 mmol of Dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP). Then the mixture was stirred at room temperature. The reaction process was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC). After completion of the reaction, the product was extracted with diethyl ether. The ether extracts were combined, washed with water and dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. The obtained products were dried, washed with water, dried again and recrystallized from methanol. Physicochemical data for compounds **II (a-i)** is given in Table no.1

A solution of **II (a-i)** 130 mg in MeOH (12ml) containing 1.0% of p-toluenesulfonic acid monohydrate (120mg) was left at 18° c for 30-45 minutes, dilute aqueous NaHCO₃ then was added, and the product (**III**) was extracted with EtOAc. The Extract was washed with H₂O, dried and concentrated in vacuo to a light glass. Recrystallized from ether.

SPECTRAL DATA OF SYNTHESIZED COMPOUNDS:

Ester of IVR with Niflumic Acid (PC1), IR v: 3327, 2930, 1733, 1698, 1625, 1607, 1532, 1447, 1383, 1330, 1310, 1229, 872-835, 774-735, 774-667. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz): δ 7.2 (5H, m, CH Ar.), δ 3.95(1H, s, NH), δ 2.29(1H, t, CH), δ 5.83(1H, d, H₉), δ 5.72 (2H, m, H10, H11), δ 5.36(1H, s, H3), δ 5.33 (1H, d, H1''), δ 4.75(1H, d, H1'), δ 4.30(1H, br d, H5), δ 3.95(1H, br s, H13) δ 3.42 (3H, s, -OCH3), δ 3.19 (1H, t, H4''), δ 3.43 (1H, d, H25), δ 2.52 (1H, m, H12), δ 1.79-1.29 (8H, m, H_{2''}, H_{2'}, H₁₈, H₂₀, H₂₄, H₂₆, H₂₇), δ 1.63 (1H, dd, H22), δ 1.52(3H, s, H14a), δ 1.25 (3H, d, H6''), δ 1.16(3H, t, H6'), δ 0.95 (3H, t, H28), δ 0.95-0.8(1H, m, H18), δ 0.87(3H, d, H26a).

Ester of IVR with Naproxen (PC2), IR v: 3612, 3227, 3030, 1736, 1626, 1484, 1437, 1418, 1390, 1379, 1346, 1311, 1269, 1229, 1160, 1104, 833, 769. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz): δ 8.2 (1H, s, CH Ar.), δ 7.2-7.3(1H, s, CH Ar.), δ 7.4-7.5(1H, d, CH Ar.), δ 3.6(3H, s, -OCH3), δ 2.3-2.4(1H, q, CH), δ 3.22(1H, t, H4''), δ 5.84(1H, d, H9), δ 5.72(2H, m, H10, H11), δ 5.35(1H, d, H1''), δ 4.64(2H, s, H8a), δ 3.77(1H, br s, 7-OH), δ 3.77(1H, d, H13), δ 3.46(1H, d, 23-OH), δ 3.42(1H, d, H25), δ 3.22(1H, s, H2), δ 2.55-2.15(5H, m, H12, H16, H2', H2''), δ 1.94(1H, dd, H22), δ 1.84(3H, s, H4a), δ 1.80-1.30(8H, m, H18, H20, H24, H26, H27), δ 1.24(3H, d, H6''), δ 1.15(3H, d, H6'), δ 0.92(3H, t, H28), δ 0.95-0.8(1H, m, H18), δ 0.88(3H, d, H26), δ 0.81(3H, d, h24).

Ester of IVR with Ibuprofen (PC3), IR v: 3612, 2928, 2850, 1739, 1626, 1547, 1536, 1436, 1382, 1346, 1229, 1186, 1159, 891, 875. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz): δ 0.89-0.92(6H, d, CH), δ 1.75-1.80(3H, d, CH), δ 1.78-1.92(1H, m, CH), δ 2.43(2H, d, CH), 7.08-7.12(1H, d, CH Ar), δ 7.21(2H, d, ArH), δ 5.39(1H, s, H3), δ 5.80-5.68(2H, m, H9, H10), δ 5.34(1H, d, H1''), δ 4.64(2H, s, H8a), δ 4.26(1H, t, H5), δ 3.86(1H, s, 7-OH), δ 3.78-3.58(3H, m, H5'', H17, H23), δ 3.40(1H, d, H25), δ 3.33(3H, s, -OCH3), δ 3.29(1H, s, H2), δ 3.18(1H, t, H4'), δ 3.18(1H, t, H4''), δ 2.0(1H, dd, H20), δ 1.84(3H, s, H4a), δ 1.80-1.30(8H, m, H2', H2'', H18, H20), δ 1.63(1H, d, H22), δ 1.55(3H, s, H14), δ 1.23(3H, d, H6''), δ 1.07(3H, d, H6'), δ 0.93(3H, t, H28), δ 0.93-0.87(1H, m, H18), δ 0.88(3H, d, H26).

Ester of IVR with Aceclofenac (PC4), IR v: 3675, 3327, 2928, 2851, 1737, 1626, 1506, 1451, 1345, 1311, 1158, 1145, 1122, 1088, 776, 746, 725. 1H-NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz): δ 7.65-7.62(2H, d, CH Ar), δ 7.55-7.52(2H, d, CH), δ 7.42-7.38(1H, d, CH Ar), δ 7.24-7.30(1H, t, CH Ar), δ 3.73(2H, s, -OCH₂), δ 5.80-5.68(2H, m H₉, H₁₀), δ 5.38(1H, s, H₃), δ 5.29(1H, d, H_{1''}), δ 5.35-5.10(3H, m, H₁₁, H₁₅, H₁₉), δ 4.75(1H, d, H_{1'}), δ 4.66(2H, s, H_{8a}), δ 4.26(1H, d, H₅), δ 3.85(1H, s, 7-OH), δ 3.78-3.58(3H, m, H_{5''}, H₁₇, H₂₃), δ 3.61(3H, s, -OH₃), δ 3.43(1H, d, H₂₅), δ 3.22(1H, s, H₂), δ 3.18(H_{4'}, t, H_{4'}), δ 2.00(1H, dd, H₂₀), δ 1.86(3H, s, H_{4a}), δ 1.63(1H, dd, H₂₂), δ 1.52(3H, s, H₁₄), δ 1.23(3H, d, H_{6''}), δ 0.93(3H, t, H₂₈), δ 0.97-0.79(1H, m, H₁₈), δ 0.83(3H, H_{24a}).

Ester of IVR with Flurbiprofen (PC5), IR v: 3675, 3317, 2928, 2851, 1737, 1626, 1506, 1451, 1345, 1311, 1158, 1145, 1122, 1088, 776, 746, 725. 1H-NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz): δ 7.50-7.47(3H, m, CH Ar), δ 7.36(3H, m, CH Ar), δ 7.17(1H, s, CH Ar), δ 1.78(3H, d, CH), δ 5.38(1H, s, H₃), δ 5.35(3H, m, H₁₁, H₁₅, H₁₉), δ 5.30(1H, d, H_{1''}), δ 4.75(1H, d, H_{1'}), δ 4.65(2H, s, H_{8a}), δ 4.26(1H, t, H₅), δ 3.93(1H, d, H₆), δ 3.85(1H, s, 7-OH), δ 3.78-3.58(3H, m, H_{5''}, H₁₇, H₂₃), δ 3.42(1H, d, H₂₅), δ 3.24(1H, s, -OCH₃), δ 3.14(1H, t, H_{4''}), δ 2.45-2.10(5H, m, H₁₂, H₁₆, H_{2'}, H_{2''}), δ 2.03(1H, dd, H₂₀), δ 1.96(1H, dd, H₂₂), δ 1.86(3H, s, H_{4a}), δ 1.52(3H, s, H_{14a}), δ 1.60-1.80(1h, m, H₁₈, H₂₀, H₂₄, H₂₆, H₂₇), δ 1.24(3H, d, H_{6''}), δ 1.16(3H, d, H_{6''}), δ 0.93(3H, t, H₂₈).

Ester of IVR with Indomethacin (PC6), IR v: 3449, 3033, 2929, 2851, 1739, 1686, 1575, 1536, 1478, 1450, 1397, 1358, 1144, 1068, 1047, 892, 874, 754.

Ester of IVR with Mefenamic Acid (PC7), IR v: 3449, 3091, 2958, 2929, 2857, 1739, 1712, 1648, 1610, 1568, 1453, 1342, 1308, 1142, 1119, 1051, 811.

Ester of IVR with Aspirin (PC7), IR v: 3372, 3033, 2958, 2851, 1743, 1709, 1683, 1626, 1574, 1449, 1437, 1345, 1311, 1142, 1087, 1068.

Ester of IVR with Salicylic acid (PC8), IR v: 3460, 3114, 2959, 1732, 1717, 1647, 1590, 1558, 1482, 1455, 1303, 1139, 1051, 765, 738.

ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY^{14, 15, 16}:

DRUGS AND CHEMICALS

Albendazole tablet (Albemint, Itrose Pharmaceuticals, Pune), Nitazoxanide (Aarti Drugs, Mumbai), Ivermectin (Pulse Pharma, Hyderabad), Saline water (Nurilife, Ahmedabad). Vehicle (2% v/v Tweens 80 in distilled water) was used.

IN-VITRO MOTILITY STUDIES:

The anthelmintic assay was carried out as per the method of Ajaiyeoba et al (14). All the synthesized products were dissolved in minimum quantity of 2%v/v Tween80 and the volume was adjusted to 20 ml with normal saline for making the concentration of 5, 10 and 20 mg/ml. six worms of approximately equal size were placed in each Petri dish containing 20 ml of above tests solution of synthesized products. Albendazole (20 mg/ml), Nitazoxanide (20 mg/ml), Ivermectin (20 mg/ml), was used as reference standard and 2% v/v Tween 80 in normal saline as a control. All the tests solution and standard drug solution were prepared freshly before starting the experiments. The anthelmintic activity was determined in six observations. Six worms of about the same size per petridish were used. They were observed for their spontaneous motility and evoked responses. Observations were made for the time taken to paralysis and death of individual worms. Paralysis was said to occur when no movement of any sort could be observed except when the worms were shaken vigorously. Time taken for death of worms were recorded after ascertaining that worms neither moved when shaken vigorously nor when dipped in warm water (50 C). Death was concluded when the worms lost their motility followed with fading away of their body color.

OBSERVATIONS:

Observations were made for time taken to paralyze in Table 3.1 and death of worms Table 3.2, which was reported in minutes.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Results were expressed as mean \pm s.e.m. Statistical significance was determined by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnett's test, with the level of significance at $P < 0.001$, $P < 0.01$ and $P < 0.05$. All compounds showed their moderate significant action for time taken to paralysis and death ($P < 0.05$) when compared with standards.

TABLE NO. 1 INDICATES THE FOUR ESTER DERIVATIVES WITH POTENT NSAIDS.

Sr. No	Compound	R	X-Y
1	Avermectin B1a	α -OH	CH=CH
2	Ivermectin	α -OH	CH ₂ CH ₂
3	Emamectin	β -MeNH	CH=CH
4	Eprinomectin	β -AcNH	CH=CH

TABLE 1: PHYSICOCHEMICAL DATA FOR COMPOUNDS PC (1-9) AND R.

Compd. No.	M. P.	Molecular Formula	% Yield	R	R _f value
PC1	75-78 ⁰ c	C ₆₇ H ₉₈ O ₁₅ N ₂ F3Si (Mol.wt 1254)	60		0.59
PC2	82-85 ⁰ c	C ₆₈ H ₁₀₃ O ₁₅ Si (Mol.wt 1203)	71		0.61
PC3	72-76 ⁰ c	C ₆₇ H ₁₀₇ O ₁₅ Si (Mol.wt 1179)	58		0.72
PC4	85-90 ⁰ c after charring	C ₇₀ H ₁₀₂ O ₁₇ NC ₂ Si (Mol.wt 1326)	61		0.49
PC5	78-82 ⁰ c	C ₆₉ H ₁₀₂ O ₁₅ FSi (Mol.wt 1217)	65		0.61
PC6	68-70 ⁰ c	C ₇₃ H ₁₀₅ O ₁₇ NC ₁ Si (Mol.wt 1330)	64		0.53
PC7	Charring	C ₆₉ H ₁₀₄ O ₁₅ NSi (Mol.wt 1214)	69		0.58
PC8	75-80 ⁰ c	C ₆₃ H ₉₇ O ₁₅ Si (Mol.wt 1153)	64		0.71
PC9	85-90 ⁰ c	C ₆₁ H ₉₅ O ₁₆ Si (Mol.wt 1111)	60		0.67

TABLE 2: SHOWING PARALYSIS TIME IN MINUTES OF TEST COMPOUND.

Test compounds	Time Taken for Paralysis (P)		
	Paralysis time (min)*		
	5mg/ml	10 mg/ml	20 mg/ml
Control	-	-	-
PC1	10.667 ± 0.33	7.50 ± 0.42	5.833 ± 0.30
PC2	12.0 ± 1.238	8.833 ± 1.10	6.333 ± 0.66
PC3	10.666 ± 0.33	8.166 ± 0.90	8.333 ± 0.84
PC4	7.5 ± 0.88	5.166 ± 0.47	4.333 ± 0.42
PC5	15.5 ± 0.56	16.5 ± 0.42	13.166 ± 0.30
PC6	11.333 ± 0.33	9.166 ± 0.47	6.666 ± 0.49
PC7	11.666 ± 0.49	9.666 ± 0.33	6.333 ± 0.33
PC8	8.5 ± 0.88	6.166 ± 0.47	5.333 ± 0.42
PC9	10.333 ± 0.49	10.166 ± 0.83	5.333 ± 0.49
Albendazole	-	-	8.83 ± 0.31
Ivermectine	-	-	14.5 ± 0.5627
Nitazoxanide	-	-	7.33±0.49

* denotes values for mean of 6 observations ± SEM p < 0.01

TABLE 3: SHOWING DEATH TIME IN MINUTES OF TEST COMPOUND.

Test compounds	Time Taken for Death (D)		
	Death time (min)*		
	5mg/ml	10 mg/ml	20 mg/ml
Control	-	-	-
PC1	15.833 ± 0.60	18.0 ± 0.25	18.5 ± 0.42
PC2	14.5 ± 1.17	15.00 ± 0.5774	10.333 ± 0.66
PC3	18.833 ± 1.138	11.333 ± 0.49	7.333 ± 0.33
PC4	10.166 ± 0.30	9.833 ± 0.54	8.333 ± 0.33
PC5	25.33 ± 1.54 ^a	26.33 ± 0.49 ^a	21.666 ± 1.116 ^a
PC6	14.166 ± 0.47	11.333 ± 0.42	10.00 ± 0.36
PC7	15.166 ± 0.47	12.5±0.4282	11.00 ± 0.36
PC8	11.333 ± 0.49	10.666±0.55	9.333 ± 0.33
PC9	28.166 ± 0.87	25.00±0.57	21.333 ± 0.49 ^b
Albendazole	-	-	18.83 ± 0.60
Ivermectine	-	-	17.833 ± 0.60
Nitazoxanide	-	-	8.5 ± 0.42

*Denotes values for mean of 6 observations ± SEM p < 0.01, a = p < 0.05, b = p > 0.05.

RESULT

The synthesis of 4th -ester derivatives with potent NSAIDs was achieved in good yield by using well known Steglich Esterification and evaluated in vitro anthelmintic activity on authenticated Indian earthworm *Pheretima posthuma*.

The Mean ± SEM, p- values calculated, by one-way ANOVA Dunnette test. The result of anthelmintic activity on earthworm *Pheretima posthuma* was given in table 2-3, reveal that, the different concentration has shown paralysis and death of earthworms and it was compared in the same concentration with Ivermectin, Albendazole and Nitazoxanide as reference drug. The compounds ester of Naproxen with Ivermectin (IIb), ester of Ibuprofen with Ivermectin (IIc), ester of Aceclofenac with Ivermectin (IId), ester of Indomethacin with Ivermectin (IIe), ester of Mefenamic with Ivermectin (IIg), ester of Aspirin with Ivermectin (IIh) exhibit little more bioactivity against earthworm species as compared with same concentration of reference drug.

DISCUSSION

The synthesis of ester analogues of Ivermectin with potent NSAIDs was achieved in good yield. The interpretation of IR and ¹H NMR spectra confirmed the structure of compounds. The IR spectra of compounds show the presence of ester group at standard value. The NMR spectra of compounds shows absence of 4th- hydroxyl group and presence of ester group along with both drugs. Statistical data give p values < 0.01, < 0.05 and > 0.05 as described in table 2 and 3.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author is thankful to The Principal, Appasaheb Birnale College of Pharmacy, Sangli for providing laboratory facility. I would like to give my sincere thanks to Prof. Shirote P. J. for his valuable suggestions and encouragement from time to time. Also, I would like to give my sincere thanks to Shivaji University, Kolhapur for providing technical assistance during my projects. We thank

Dr. Sandhya Pawar, Assistant Professor, Department of Zoology, Padmabhushan Dr. Vasantdada Patil Mahavidyalaya, Tasgaon, India for her help in worm authentication.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors don't have conflict of interest

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